

SHORT COMMUNICATIONS

Ethylenediamine Complex of Bivalent Rhenium

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A series of cyano¹ and substituted cyano^{2,3} compounds of rhenium (II) have been reported earlier. The present note reports the isolation of a new substituted tetracyano compound with ethylene-diamine as the substituent. It is interesting in that the substituent ligand is not a π -acceptor.

Sodium pentacyanoaquo-rhenate (II) was prepared by the method described by Sen¹. A concentrated aqueous solution was refluxed on a water bath with a slight excess of one equivalent of ethylenediamine hydrate. After 2 hr, the product was cooled and treated with ethanol. An orange coloured oil was separated which on treatment with absolute alcohol changed to a dirty yellow solid. This was washed with absolute alcohol. The solid was then dissolved in minimum quantity of water and was just acidified with 1 : 1 acetic acid. The mixture was evaporated in vacuum over conc. H₂SO₄. The mass was then repeatedly washed with rectified spirit till it was free from sodium acetate and finally with absolute alcohol to give a slightly hygroscopic yellow powder. This was dried over conc. H₂SO₄ in vacuum and analysed.

Found : Re, 46.3 ; Na, 11.7 ; N, 21.1%

Calculated for Na₉[Re^{II}(CN)₄en] : Re, 46.7 ; Na, 11.6 ; N, 21.2%

The sodium salt is highly soluble in water but insoluble in methyl and ethyl alcohols, acetone etc. The aqueous solution is quite stable.

Qualitative reactions with certain metal ions are given below :

<i>Cations</i>	<i>Reactions</i>
Fe ³⁺	Blue ppt.
Cr ³⁺	Green ppt.
Co ²⁺	Deep green ppt., on standing turns brown.
Ni ²⁺	Yellow green ppt.
Fe ²⁺	Greenish white ppt.
Hg ²⁺	Yellow ppt.
Pb ²⁺	Yellow ppt.
Cu ²⁺	Pink ppt., on standing turns brown.
Zn ²⁺	Yellow ppt.
Mn ²⁺	White ppt.
Ag ⁺	Yellow brown ppt.

1. S. Sen, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1962, 315, 315.

2. Idem, *ibid.*, 1965, 340, 82.

3. B. K. Sen, N. N. Ghosh and P. B. Sarkar, *Sci. & Cult.*, 1962, 28, 290, 387 ; 1963, 29, 201.

Aqueous solution of the salt is oxidised by KMnO_4 in $\text{N-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ medium. Potentiometric titration indicates an one-electron change reaction which may be written as.

The salt is diamagnetic at 302°K.

Further work is in progress, the details of which will be published later. The author expresses his sincere gratitude to Dr. P. Bandyopadhyay and Professor P. B. Sarkar, for their suggestions and interest in the work. Thanks are also due to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

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